

Issue: Contemporary trends in Language Studies

Revista Letras Raras, a scholarly journal of Linguistics and Literature, from the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity (Federal University of Campina Grande, UFCG), launches its fourth regular edition of 2022. This issue is organised by professors Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFCG, Brazil), Maria Rennally Soares da Silva, from both the State University of Paraíba (UEPB, Brazil) and UFCG, as well as by professor Alain Philippe Durand, from the University of Arizona (United States of America).

The seven papers that make up the issue *Contemporary trends in Language Studies* are situated in the fields of Social Interactionism, Critical Discourse Analysis, Interactional Sociolinguistics, Literary Studies, and Decolonial Studies; besides two interviews, two reviews, and nine texts of artistic creation. This edition has the collaboration of professors, students, and other researchers who are authors of the papers, interviews, reviews and texts of artistic or literary creation, coming from different origins, such as: Federal University of Fronteira Sul (UFFS), University of Brasilia (UnB), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), Federal University of Grande Dourados (UFGD), Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Amazonas (IFAM), Federal Rural University of Pernambuco (UFRPE), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Feevale University, La Salle University, Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), State University of Rio de Janeiro / Faculty of Teacher Training (UERJ/FFP), Federal University of Paraná (UFPR), Federal University of Piauí (UFPI), Federal University of Goiás (UFG), and Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG).

In this fourth and last edition of the year, the estimated reader shall read and share the texts of this issue by also pointing your mobile camera to the QR Code of the journal and of the text you wish to. Dear reader, we hope you share the paper, the interview, the review, and the artistic productions from this issue with your colleagues and students.

We come to the end of this year full o hopes for the new paths Brazil is taking, expecting they evoke tolerance, respect, equity, and a focus on the investment in Education and Science, as well as in the education for all!

In the certainty of this sharing, dear reader, we wish you a great reading!

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Editors of **Revista Letras Raras**: a Scholarly Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral